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Practices for Quality Management System Adopted in the Bridge Construction Projects of Kathmandu, Nepal

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Abstract

Quality management in the project has significant implication from an economic view as well as social point of view. Bridge construction project is located in the local road networks focus on many problems and complex issues among which can be effectively over run by quality management process. The objective of this research is to identify the best system for quality management in bridge construction project. This study is based on the questionnaire with the clients, consultant, contractor who are involved in Bridge construction project. A comprehensive literature review was deployed to generate a set of factors related to Quality management process. In total 84 questionnaires were distributed with the response rate 94.047% to the three key group of projects participants: Contractor, Consultancy and Clients. This involved study of 28 bridges of Local Road Bridge network of Kathmandu district which are in construction phase, completed phase under DoLIDAR, JICA, DDC, RAIDP, DRILP, and RTISWAP. The importance of the individual factors and the group are calculated and ranked by the irrelative important index. Total Quality Management, Quality Assurance and Quality Control ranked highest respectively as a part of quality management practices being followed in projects. The outcome of this study will document the quality management system and assist to improve the quality system of bridge construction project. It focuses to provide a tool and idea for quality management improvement for the sector. It will also assist the contractor, consultancy and clients in understanding the better practices for quality management system in bridge construction process.

Keywords: Control Methods, Necessary Measures, ISO Standards

Background

Quality in the construction industry has long been a problem in Nepal. It has been reflected in certain serious accidents in the past. There are numerous accidents that had arisen out of poor quality in bridge construction but could not be reported. The quality issue in Nepal though exists generally, great expenditures of time and resources are wasted each year because of inefficient or non-existent quality management system.

Nepal is a country with the huge variation in topography. Approximately 80% of the total of the country is occupied by hills and mountains (SDC, 2010). The topography is

extremely rugged and crisscrossed by numerous rivers and streams. There are more than 6,000 rivers and rivulets (TBSU, 2010). Thus, it is very clear that the need of bridges to cross those rivers and rivulets is very high.

Under Department of Local Infrastructure Development and Agricultural Roads (DoLIDAR), at present condition, bridges are constructed through different programmes and projects like, Local Road Bridge Programme (LRBP) funded by the Government of Nepal, the project for Improvement of Community Access in Nepal (CAIP) funded by Government of Japan, Rural Reconstruction and Rehabilitation Sector Development Programme (RRRSDP) funded by Asian Development Bank, Decentralized Rural Infrastructure

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and Livelihood Programme (DRILP), funded by Asian Development Bank, Rural Transport Infrastructure Sector Wide Programme (RTISWAP), 30% contribution by the respective DDDC's and 70% by the central government and Rural Accessibility Improvement and Decentralization Project (RAIDP) funded by World Bank in different districts. Local Road Bridge Support Unit through SDC will provide technical support to the bridges financially supported by GON as well as to the bridges supported by various donor agencies. Altogether there are more than 200 bridges in under construction and design phase in Local Road Network and in fiscal year 2014/ 2015 DoLIDAR has carried a walk over survey of 69 bridges throughout the country (DoLIDAR, 2014). The Nepalese Bridge construction projects are facing the problems related with measuring and improving techniques for quality performance. Accordingly, this research work is being undertaken to explore as to what formal quality management systems are taken to ensure the quality in Bridge construction works in Nepal in general.

Research Objectives

The overall objective of the research is to find out practices for quality management system adopted in the Bridge construction projects.

Lterature Review

Quality Approach

Garvin (1984) identifies several approaches to quality, each with different implication for quality control and quality improvement. Garvin presents five approaches to quality

as Transcendent Approach, Product-Based Approach, User-Based Approach, Manufacturing-Based Approach and Value-Based Approach and eight dimensions such as performance, features, reliability, Conformance, Durability, Aesthetics, perceived quality and Serviceability.

Quality Management

The first step in the quality management process is up to top management. What is the company's policy toward quality? While this may seem simple, it is the essence of the entire quality effort. The policy should be given a great deal of thought. Quality management includes Quality Assurance (QA) and Quality Control (QC) as well as other concepts of quality planning, quality policy and quality improvement. Total Quality Management (TQM) develops these concepts as long as term global management strategy and the participation of all members of the organization for benefit of the organization itself, its members, its customers and society as a whole.

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Figure 1. Quality Management

(Source: Oakland, 1995)

The system of documentation and application of responsibilities for achieving is a quality management system (QMS). It assures the well-defended objectives and process for getting the same.

Quality management systems serve many purposes, including: Improving processes

- Reducing waste
- Lowering costs
- Facilitating and identifying training opportunities
- Engaging staff
- Setting organization-wide direction

assurance standards are designed for contractual and assessment purposes and is ISO 9001, ISO 9002, and ISO 9003. The quality management standard is ISO 9004 and is designed to provide guidance for companies developing and implementing quality systems. A company registered as complying with ISO standards has demonstrated to an accredited third party (an approved outside auditor) that its processes have been documented and that the company is systematically auditing and being audited that they are following the policies and procedures necessary to produce high quality products. ISO standards are directed towards improving a firm’s production processes. A TQM

Figure 2. Illustration of Relationship of QMS and TQM

(Source: Kanji, 1998)

These total quality management concepts can be put into place by any organization to more effectively implement total quality management.

The Quality Standard

The implementation of formal quality assurance procedures can bring:

- Better design
- More effective planning
- Improved site management
- Increased project performance
- Efficient management of construction problems
- Improved quality
- Fewer delays and disruptions
- Lower cost of remedial and repeat works

ISO Standards

The Geneva-based International Organization for Standardization first published a series of standards in 1987. The term ISO describes the series of international standards dealing with product design, production, delivery and service and testing. The ISO 9000 series comprises two basic types of standard: that addressing quality assurance and that addressing quality management. The quality

system is the big picture and covers all activities conducted by a firm including customer satisfaction. A good way of viewing ISO is that the emphasis in the ISO registration is on the management of process quality. This is not meant to minimize the role of ISO in a TQM system. The ISO standards provide an excellent beginning point for a firm starting a TQM program.

Figure 3. ISO 9000 prevents losing ground

Source: (Arditi, 1998)

Brief description of twenty elements of ISO standard

1. **Management Responsibility:** Quality Policy reflecting the organization’s attitude to quality and ensure it is

communicated throughout the organization. Allocating the appropriate resources and trained personnel to perform the work and appointment of a management representative to monitor the Quality System. Conduct regular management reviews to ensure the health of the quality system.

2. **Quality System:** formal way of documented demand collection.
3. **Contract Review:** it should be continuous review of contract for effective implementation.
4. **Design Control:** All phases of product or service design (engineering) must be controlled and conducted by qualified personnel. (This pertains to ISO-9001 only.)
5. **Document and Data Control:** Always make the things visible which is invisible all the time for documentation and controlling.
6. **Purchasing:** Purchasing information must be complete and accurate. Suppliers must be qualified and selected based on demonstrated quality. Suppliers must be monitored continuously.
7. **Control of Customer Supplied Product**

If and when customers supply the materials for their products, you must ensure that:

- you report to the customers any discrepancy or damage to their products.
 - Their products can be identified easily.
 - Their products are handled and stored accordingly.
8. **Identification and Traceability:** Products must be identified at all times and through all phases of production.
 9. **Process Control:** You are required to have a complete process, with appropriate written procedures, to perform and monitor all production activities, which affect quality.
 10. **Inspection:** You are required to have documented verifications at all critical stages of your process:
 - Receiving of raw material.
 - Work in process.
 - Final inspection.
 11. **Calibration:** All inspection and measuring equipment (Gauges, thermometers, scales, test software...) must be controlled and maintained in calibration. You are required to:
 - Provide unique identification and list of all inspection and measuring equipment.
 - Determine the required accuracy.
 - Protect and maintain the equipment to ensure continuing accuracy.
 - Calibrate each instrument on a pre-determined cycle to established procedures.

12. **Inspection and Test Status:** Process is effective though final product need to be assessed.
13. **Control of Nonconforming Product:** Any nonconforming product must be properly identified and segregated (if practical) with a documented disposition.
14. **Corrective and Preventive Action:** You are required to have a formal process to correct and prevent problems from occurring. The process will ensure that:
 - Root cause is investigated
 - Corrective and/ or preventive action is taken
 - The effectiveness of corrective and/ or preventive is verified
15. **Handling, Storage, Packaging, Preservation and Delivery:** Required to have documented procedures for:
 - Handling
 - Storage
 - Packaging
 - Preservation
 - Delivery
16. **Control of Quality Records:** Records which demonstrate compliance to procedures and ISO-9000 must be:
 - Identified
 - Legible
 - Accurate
 - Filed and indexed properly
 - Easily retrievable
 - Retained for a specified period of time
17. **Internal Quality Audits:** You are required to conduct formal internal audits to examine all activities affecting quality, and evaluate their compliance to:
 - Documented procedures
 - ISO 9000 requirements.\
18. **Training:** It is needed to identify appropriate training and provide with proper documentation of training activities. It is also need to ensure only trained people carry activities affecting product quality.
19. **Servicing:** If you provide “servicing” as part of the contract, you are required to control:
 - The design and use of the service equipment.
 - Use trained and qualified personnel.
 - Ensure product and parts availability.
 - Document working procedures and methods.
20. **Statistical Techniques:** Any data analysis, sampling methods, and SPC used must be based on established procedures and sound statistical techniques.

Management Practices in Construction Sector in Nepal

Nepalese management practices are largely traditional. There is deep rooted traditional management thinking and practices in construction industries (Bhisam, 2010). Modern management concept and practices are relatively new. Poor planning has been a problem in most construction industries. The participative attitudes that manager adopt in the management of the people has also proved to be a barrier against effective management. Communication systems are defective and upward communication is often ignored. Most construction industries face behavioral problems, such as lack of motivation and trust, negative attitude to work, difficult interpersonal relation (Bhisam, 2010).

Methodology

Description of Bridges used for study

Among twenty eight bridges of district road network in only Kathmandu district is taken as sample for our research study. They are selected only for ecological region i.e covering mountain region.

All the observed bridges are in district road network and constructed by DoLIDAR, DDC, JICA, RAIDP, DRILP and RTISWAP through different programs and projects. They are different types which include RCC Girder Bridge open foundation, well foundation, cable stayed bridge, steel truss; steel plate girder and some are PSC. The span of bridge ranges from 4.55 m to 133 m. The sample are taken in such a way that it includes both solely government funded and donor funded bridges and are implemented by central level as well as district evel. The bridge includes both the completed and under construction bridges which are lagging behind the schedules. The sample covers the bridge having progress of 25-100%. The population of the study for questionnaire survey consisted of clients, consultants and contractors involved in district bridges construction sector.

Collection of Data and Information

Primary data were collected through survey questionnaire with clients, consultant and contractor.

Primary data

The primary data were collected from survey questionnaire. As in many development related researchers, specific check lists were provided. The analytical inductive techniques based on questionnaire with semi-structured, structured and open-ended questions, have been applied. The major techniques of primary data collection is:

- Schedules/ Questionnaire

An interview checklist was developed to collect people's perception, understanding and view regarding the quality management aspect of the bridge project. The questionnaire is divided into 4 main parts.

Part I is related to general information of organization.

Part II is related with which practices for quality management system are adopted in the Bridge construction projects.

- Practices for quality management system adopted in the Bridge construction projects.
- Achieving quality on projects
- Ranking of twenty elements of ISO standard
- Quality control measure

Secondary Data

The secondary data was collected from the following sources:

- Report produced by the SDC
- Publications of NPC, MoFALD, DoLIDAR and DoR
- Documents and reports of LRBSU
- Documents and reports of LRBP program office and DDC/ DTOs.
- Quality assurance plan (QAP) of different bridge projects within studied population.

Processing data

After collection of data, it was edited for completeness, consistency, accuracy and homogeneity.

Data compilation and analysis

All the data and information collected from the primary sources were analyzed by comparing and contrasting the situation. The collected data are presented on the basis of quality and nature of data. The qualitative data are presented to develop the logic sequential whereas the quantitative data are presented in table, figure and percentage.

Response Rate

In order to identify the factors affecting the quality management of bridge construction and best quality management process and who should be responsible for enforcing the quality assurance practices questionnaire survey is conducted. The questionnaire was distributed to clients, consultants and contractors. The questionnaire is divided into 7 main parts. The response rate of client is 100%, for consultancy is 96.43% and contractor is 85.71%.

Table 1. Response to Questionnaire Administered

Distributed to	No. of distributed	No. of replied	Questionnaire return (%)	Remarks
Client	28	28	100	-
Consultant	28	27	96.43	One consultant involved in two different projects
Contractor	28	24	85.71	Four contractor involved in more than one project
Total	84	79	94.05	

Working Experience of Respondents

In questionnaire survey all the respondent are asked for their work experience and field of experience. It is found that 11 respondent have less than 3 years of experience and 14 of them have more than 10 years of work experience. 30 of respondent work in Road construction and 28 of them work for bridge construction.

Table 2. Work Experience of Respondents

Industrial Experience	Clients	Consultant	Contractor	Total
Under 3 years	6	4	1	11
3-5 years	8	8	12	28
5-10 Years	10	11	5	26
Over 10 years	4	4	6	14
Total	28	27	24	79

Statistical tools used for Data Processing

The statistical method used for analyzing the data can be briefly explained as:

Mean Value (X)

The minimum, maximum and the average arithmetic mean (X) values for each issues in the question have been calculated for each group to identify the extreme and average opinion on the issue as:

$$\text{Mean value (X)} = \frac{X_1 + X_2 + \dots + X_n}{N}$$

Where,

N= number of respondent

xi=n= numeric rating given by each respondents

Standard Deviation (SD)

The standard deviation (Sd) in the rating from each group of respondents has been calculated to evaluated the dispersion of the obtained data. It is the measurement for how widely the values are dispersed from the mean value. If the standard deviation is low the accuracy of the

data is high or most of the respondent ratings or opinion were closer. The standard deviation is calculated as:

Standard Deviation

$$SD = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (N_x - \bar{X})^2}{(N - 1)}}$$

Where,

Xi= numeric rating given by each respondents

X= Mean Value

N= number of respondent

Relative Importance Index (RII)

The RII was to evaluate the ratings of the respondents. This approach is recommended in the past studies (Olusegun, 2011) as appropriate analytical approach to groups rating of the variable in a given set. The analysis involved the computation of RII, which is representative rating point for the collective rating made for each variable in the subset. Using the following equation the relative importance index of each sub-factor was calculated as:

Relative Importance Index

$$RII = \frac{\sum W_i}{N * A}$$

Where,

Wi= The rating given to each factor by the respondents ranging from 1-4

N= Total no. of respondent

A= Large rating score from respondent

Kendall's Coefficient of Concordance (W-test)

Kendall's coefficient of concordance, represented by the symbol W, is an important non-parametric measure of relationship. It is used for determining the degree of association among several (k) sets of ranking of N objects or individuals. When there are only two sets of rankings of N objects, we generally work out Spearman's coefficient of correlation, but Kendall's coefficient of concordance (W) is considered an appropriate measure of studying the degree

of association among three or more sets of rankings.

The procedure for computing and interpreting Kendall's coefficient of concordance (W) is as follows:

- All the objects, N, should be ranked by all K parties in the usual fashion and this information may be put in the form of a K by N matrix
- For each object determine the sum of ranks (R_j) assigned by all the K parties
- Determine R_j and the n obtain the value of s as under

$$s = \sum_{j=1}^k (R_j - \bar{R}_j)^2$$
- Work out the value of W using the following formula

$$W = \frac{s}{\frac{1}{12}k^2(N^3 - N)}$$
- The method for judging whether the calculated value of W is significantly different from zero depends on the size of N as stated below:
- If N is 7 or smaller, Table No. 9 given in appendix at the end of the book gives critical values of S associated with W's significance at 5% and 1% levels. If an observed S is equal to or greater than that shown in the table for a particular level of significance, then H₀T (i.e., K sets of rankings are independent) may be rejected at that level of significance.

Testing of Hypotheses-II309

If N is larger than 7, we may use χ^2 value to be worked out as: $\chi^2 = k(N-1) \cdot W$

With d.f. = (N-1) for judging W's significance at a given level in the usual way of using χ^2 values

where, χ^2 is a statistical measure used in the context of sampling analysis for comparing a variance to a theoretical variance. It can also be used to make comparisons between theoretical populations and actual data when categories are used.

$$\chi^2 = \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{(O_i - E_i)^2}{E_i}$$

where, the subscript "c" are the degrees of freedom. "O" is observed value and E is expected value.

Table 3. Ranking of practices for quality management system adopted in the Bridge construction projects

Quality System	Clients		Consultant		Contractor		Overall	
	RII	Rank	RII	Rank	RII	Rank	RII	Rank
Total Quality Management	0.750	3	0.852	1	0.625	4	0.742	1
Quality Management System	0.817	1	0.537	5	0.781	1	0.712	5
Quality Control	0.758	2	0.833	2	0.604	5	0.732	3
Quality Improvement	0.742	4	0.769	4	0.635	3	0.715	4
Quality Assurance	0.633	5	0.815	3	0.760	2	0.736	2
Others	0.000	0	0.000	0	0.000	0	0.000	6

Mean Item Score

MIS is used for ranking the significant factor obtained from interview. MIS=Average value

Result and Discussion

Survey questionnaire was done to find the best and effective quality system. As shown in Table 3, client and contract or give the main priority to the quality management system and consultant give total quality management as main priority. In overall Total Quality Management ranked 1st scoring RII 0.742, Quality assurance ranked 2nd and Quality control ranked 3rd.

Null hypothesis: H₀: There is no any degree of agreement among clients, contractors and consultants.

Alternative hypothesis: H₁: There is a statistically significant degree of agreement among clients, contractors and consultants.

To judge the significance degree of agreement between clients, consultant and contractor W-test is done, looking into the Table 7.5.21 given in appendix E, we reject the null hypothesis and infer that the parties are applying essentially the same standard in ranking the N objects i.e., there is significant agreement in ranking by different parties at 5% level.

Achieving Quality in Projects

Survey questionnaire was given to all clients, consultant and contractor find out better practices for achieving quality in projects. Customer expectation got major priority by contractor and consultant while clients give work improvement teams major priority. Desirable results, safe work procedures, data and information are some important practices.

Null hypothesis: H₀: There is no any degree of agreement among clients, contractors and consultants.

Alternative hypothesis: H₁: There is a statistically significant degree of agreement among clients, contractors and consultants.

Table 4. Ranking of Practices to achieve quality in projects

Practices	Clients		Consultant		Contractor		Overall	
	RII	Rank	RII	Rank	RII	Rank	RII	Rank
Management commitment and involvement	0.558	18	0.615	18	0.656	4	0.610	16
Customer Expectation	0.625	7	0.847	1	0.719	1	0.730	1
Recorded outcomes and achievements	0.642	6	0.688	7	0.563	18	0.631	12
Benchmarking	0.575	15	0.646	17	0.594	12	0.605	17
Desirable Results	0.667	4	0.771	2	0.604	11	0.681	3
Work improvement teams	0.744	1	0.708	6	0.583	15	0.679	4
Training and Education in quality	0.608	11	0.677	10	0.615	10	0.633	11
Reward System/ Incentives	0.525	19	0.656	15	0.542	19	0.574	19
Data and Information	0.625	7	0.688	7	0.688	2	0.667	6
Procurement of equipment and material	0.592	13	0.594	19	0.625	8	0.603	18
Levels of output or productivity	0.650	5	0.656	15	0.583	15	0.630	13
Profitability	0.683	3	0.750	3	0.646	6	0.693	2
Mission statement, vision and values	0.617	9	0.667	13	0.646	6	0.643	9
Short-term view	0.592	13	0.740	4	0.656	4	0.663	7
Measurement of Outcomes	0.617	9	0.677	10	0.583	15	0.626	15
Innovation and creativity	0.575	15	0.719	5	0.625	8	0.640	10
Safe Work Procedures (SWPs)	0.742	2	0.667	13	0.594	12	0.667	5
Contractor ISO 9000 series certification	0.575	15	0.677	10	0.688	2	0.647	8
Designer ISO 9000 series certification	0.600	12	0.688	7	0.594	12	0.627	14

Table 5. Ranking of Twenty Elements of ISO Standard

Elements	Clients		Consultant		Contractor		Overall	
	RII	Rank	RII	Rank	RII	Rank	RII	Rank
Management Responsibility	0.509	17	0.519	16	0.594	17	0.540	17
Quality System	0.446	19	0.444	19	0.521	19	0.471	19
Contract Review	0.732	7	0.741	7	0.854	8	0.776	7
Design Control	0.429	20	0.426	20	0.500	20	0.451	20
Document and Data Control	0.643	11	0.648	11	0.750	12	0.680	11
Purchasing	0.545	14	0.556	13	0.635	14	0.579	14
Control of Customer Supplied Product	0.527	15	0.537	15	0.615	15	0.559	15
Identification and Traceability	0.732	7	0.731	8	0.854	8	0.773	8
Process Control	0.768	4	0.778	4	0.896	4	0.814	4
Inspection	0.741	6	0.750	6	0.865	7	0.785	6
Calibration	0.482	18	0.481	18	0.563	18	0.509	18
Inspection and Test Status	0.679	9	0.694	9	0.792	10	0.722	9
Control of Nonconforming Product	0.857	1	0.861	1	1.000	1	0.906	1
Corrective and Preventive Action	0.527	15	0.519	16	0.615	15	0.553	16
Handling, Storage, Packaging, Preservation and Delivery	0.830	2	0.843	2	0.969	2	0.881	2

Control of Quality Records	0.768	4	0.769	5	0.896	4	0.811	5
Internal Quality Audits	0.821	3	0.824	3	0.958	3	0.868	3
Training	0.563	13	0.556	13	0.875	6	0.664	13
Servicing	0.679	9	0.676	10	0.792	10	0.715	10
Statistical Techniques	0.634	12	0.639	12	0.740	13	0.671	12

To judge the significance degree of agreement between clients, consultant and contractor

W-test is done, looking into the Table 7.5.2 given in appendix E value of χ^2 is Considerably higher than the table value. This does not support the null hypothesis of independence and as such we can infer that it supports alternate hypothesis thus W is significant at 95% level.

Ranking of the twenty elements of ISO standard

Control of nonconforming product ranked 1st whereas design control ranked last as shown in Table 5. Handling, storage, packaging, preservation and delivery ranked 2nd and internal quality audits ranked 3rd.

Null hypothesis: H0: There is no any degree of agreement among clients, contractors and consultants.

Alternative hypothesis: H1: There is a statistically significant degree of agreement among clients, contractors and consultants.

To judge the significance degree of agreement between clients, consultant and contractor W-test is done, looking

Quality Control Method

In order to find out the better quality management need to be adopted in Bridge construction process. Respondent are asked different methods for maintaining the quality in bridge construction. In questionnaire, respondents are asked to give rating which they prefer. We can conclude that overall all respondent agreed that material selection and usage should be given higher priority and inspection and testing of executed works in 2nd.

Null hypothesis: H0: There is no any degree of agreement among clients, contractors and consultants.

Alternative hypothesis: H1: There is a statistically significant degree of agreement among clients, contractors and consultants.

To judge the significance degree of agreement between clients, consultant and contractor W-test is done, looking into the Table 7.5.4 given in appendix E, reject the null hypothesis and infer that the parties are applying essentially the same standard in ranking the N objects i.e., there is significant agreement in ranking by different parties at 95% level.

Table 6. Respondents response on Quality control method

Quality control method	Clients		Consultancy		Contractor		Overall	
	RII	Rank	RII	Rank	RII	Rank	RII	Rank
Use of code of conduct	0.558	6	0.546	6	0.583	5	0.563	6
Materials selection and usage	0.625	4	0.753	1	0.646	2	0.675	1
Construction process adopted	0.642	3	0.611	4	0.646	2	0.633	4
Recording changes	0.575	5	0.574	5	0.656	1	0.602	5
Report of nonconformity to quality standards	0.667	2	0.685	2	0.583	5	0.645	3
Inspection and testing of executed works	0.744	1	0.630	3	0.625	4	0.666	2

into the Table 7.5.3 given in appendix E, value of χ^2 is considerably higher than the table value. This does not support the null hypothesis of

Independence as our calculated value i.e. it supports the alternate hypothesis and as such we can infer that W is significant at 95% level.

Measures Needed to Ensure Effective Compliance to Quality Standards

From major respondents agree that providing training and seminar on quality assurance and enforcement of quality standards by government and/ or other agency in project delivery help to ensure effective compliance to quality

Table 7. Frequency compliance to quality standards in Construction of Bridges

Necessary Measures	Frequency	Total	Percentage (%)
Provide training and seminar on quality assurance	28	79	35.44
Support the setting up of quality assurance department in construction firms	12	79	15.19
Enforcement of quality standards by government and/ or other agency in project delivery	21	79	26.58
Severe penalty for noncompliance to quality standards by government/ professional bodies	8	79	10.13
Enforce statutory requirement	10	79	12.66

standards in Construction of Bridges.

Conclusion

Total quality management system ranked 1st scoring RII of 0.742 and quality assurance ranked 2nd scoring RII 0.736. Quality control ranked 3rd, Quality improvement ranked 4th and Quality management system ranked 5th. Respondents didn't specify any other intervention than included. In finding the governing elements of ISO Standards, control of non-confirming products ranked first, handling, storage, packaging, preservation and delivery ranked second and Internal Quality Audits was ranked third. After completion of survey most of the respondent says providing training and seminar on quality assurance helps to ensure effective compliance to quality standard in bridge construction while some other respondent says enforcement of quality standards by government and/ or other agency in project delivery or Support the setting up of quality assurance department in construction firms helps.

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